

Simulation Development of a Forward Sensor-Enhanced Low-Altitude Guidance System

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ABSTRACT

The requirement to operate aircraft at low-altitude near the terrain is common in the military community and essential for helicopters. The risk and crew workload in this flight regime is severe, with navigation, guidance, and obstacle avoidance demanding high attention. A guidance system relying on digitized terrain elevation maps has been developed that employs airborne navigation, mission requirements, aircraft performance limits, and radar altimeter returns to generate a valley-seeking, low-altitude trajectory between waypoints for display to the pilot. This system has been flight demonstrated to 150 ft above ground level altitude, and is primarily limited by the ability of the pilot to perform obstacle detection and avoidance. In this study, a wide field of view forward sensor has been modeled and incorporated in the guidance system for the purpose of relieving the pilot of the obstacle avoidance duty. The results of a piloted, motion-based simulation of this enhanced low-altitude guidance system is presented. Simulated flights to 50 ft altitude in the presence of obstacles were demonstrated while maintaining situational awareness and close tracking of the guidance trajectory.

INTRODUCTION

En route flight operations near the ground or in poor weather have received much attention due to their high workload and inherent risk. Advances in computational capacity, sensor capability, and signal processing have produced a variety of avionic aids for this flight regime. Much of the emphasis has focused on the ability to detect and avoid obstacles through both passive sensors such as forward looking infrared and low-level light television, and with active sensors like radar. Obstacle location is typically provided to the pilot on any combination of head-down or head-up displays. The pilot is traditionally obligated to perform remaining functions such as navigation and guidance while attempting to employ his obstacle detection capability. The integration of these functions in a synergistic manner is a difficult challenge, primarily due to their component, mission, and aircraft specific nature [1-4].

A technology development program at NASA Ames Research Center in helicopter flight automation [5] has included the development of a low-altitude, maneuvering terrain following/terrain avoidance (TF/TA) guidance system for helicopters [6]. The guidance algorithm uses mission requirements, aircraft performance capabilities, navigational data, and digitized terrain elevation data to generate a low-altitude, valley-seeking trajectory. This trajectory is generated in real-time and presented to the pilot on a helmet-mounted display. The system's flight envelope is principally limited in its ability to position itself within the terrain (due to airborne navigation and terrain database errors), and its inability to detect and avoid unmapped obstacles, such as trees and wires. To improve above-ground-level positioning of the baseline guidance system, a Kalman filter was developed that augments this system through the integration of a radar altimeter [7]. After evaluation in several piloted simulations, the system was implemented for flight evaluation aboard the U.S. Army's NUH-60 STAR (Systems Testbed for Avionics Research) test helicopter. Operation to 150 ft above ground level (AGL) altitude in good visibility has been demonstrated in flight [8, 9].

To allow flight at even lower altitudes and in poor visibility, a forward-looking sensor must be incorporated to locate unmapped obstacles and provide a near-field, look-ahead capability. In this work, a wide field of view sensor was modeled and integrated into the guidance system. The sensor's returns were used to generate an inertially stored, aircraft centered obstacle database. The trajectory was then altered to avoid terrain and obstacles along its path, allowing for reduced altitude operation.

The paper begins with a description of the baseline low-altitude guidance system considered, along with the forward sensor enhancement. The piloted motion-based simulation is then detailed, and results presented. Concluding remarks and future directions are then provided.

for that area, and can be greater than the general database accuracy objectives [10]. Because the terrain elevation stored in the DMA database is accessed via the latitude-longitude value of the navigation system, horizontal positioning errors will reference offset terrain data. The sum of these errors, combined with vertical navigation error, can lead to large errors in the predicted absolute AGL altitude. This problem was addressed by blending radar altimeter measurements with airborne navigation and terrain elevation data in estimating AGL altitude. The minimum operating altitude of the guidance system was demonstrated in flight evaluation to be reduced from 300 ft to 150 ft with the addition of a Kalman filter state estimator [9].

Typical terrain databases, including the (most) common Level 1 DMA DTED, register the ground height only and include no information regarding man-made or natural obstacles. Common obstacles such as wires and trees must be detected and avoided by other means, typically by the pilot. This results in restrictions in the operating speed, flight altitude, and visibility minimums of the CALAHF guidance system. The integration of a forward sensor for obstacle detection and subsequent guidance trajectory modification can potentially lower these obstacle-generated flight envelope constraints.

Forward Sensor

The forward sensor model was based on the Obstacle Avoidance System (OASYS) prototype sensor under development by the U.S. Army Night Vision Electro-Optics Directorate (NVEOD), Ft. Belvoir, VA. The OASYS employs a gallium arsenide diode based laser radar to locate obstacles in a $25^\circ \times 50^\circ$ field of view (FOV). The fixed forward sensor scans this FOV with a holographic optical element in 0.75 sec. The sensor attempts to detect all obstacles in this FOV, particularly wires [11].

The simulation sensor model was fixed to the chin of the helicopter, along its centerline. It nominally was of $25^\circ \times 50^\circ$ field of view at 1° resolution and range of 4922 ft (1500 m). The sweep pattern of the resulting 1250 "beams" was from top to bottom, left to right. Terrain or obstacle strikes by a given beam were determined through line-of-sight calculations every 33 ft (10 m) along each beam. Any obstacle or terrain strike would be registered and output for storage to an inertially-referenced database. No attributes were associated with a beam strike, i.e. a tree and the ground itself are indistinguishable. The next beam in sequence would be considered after a strike registered, or upon reaching the sensors maximum range, whichever occurred first. The forward sensor would thus serve to locate obstacles deposited in the computer generated imagery of which the guidance algorithm was unaware.

Sensor Generated Database

The terrain or obstacles located by the forward sensor are stored in an inertially-referenced grid system with grid resolution of (33 ft (10 m)). The area considered by the guidance system is 9843 ft (3000 m) square and is periodically shifted through the grid system such that its center position remains approximately below the aircraft. This allows previously obtained sensor information to be retained and available for trajectory planning. Objects intersected by the forward sensor beams are registered by the sensor's central elevation, central azimuth, and range. The center of the beam with respect to elevation and azimuth angle is required as the 1° beam width spreads into multiple grids with increasing range. These values are then transformed to aircraft body and then to inertial coordinates. The resulting z or height value is then assigned to the 33 ft grid square in which its x, y value is contained. Any later object measurements that fall into the same quantized grid simply overwrite the existing height value. All grids are initialized with a height value of -1 ft.

Path Manager

The path manager is used in altering the baseline guidance trajectory before presentation to the pilot on the helmet mounted display. That is, the solely airborne navigation and stored terrain elevation database referenced trajectory of the baseline CALAHF system, $[\rho_{traj}]$, is modified with respect to the forward sensor created obstacle and terrain database to produce $[\rho'_{traj}]$ (Fig 1). The path manager compares the baseline trajectory with the obstacle database created by the forward sensor. All sensor database grids (33 ft square) within a 200 ft diameter (the width of the top of the troughs) of the center of each trajectory trough are considered for the comparison. The upper section of Fig. 3 portrays the trough comparison circle and values calculated. For each trough comparison circle, the maximum (δ_{max}^n) and the local average (δ_{ave}^n) of the elevation differences between the sensor grids in the diameter around each trough and that of the DMA are calculated. The averages are not weighted with degree of trough comparison circle coverage. Errors between the baseline trajectory and obstacle database of greater than 1 ft were registered and used to alter the nominal trajectory in the vertical plane. Three methods of achieving this "safe-guarding" of the trajectory were considered in the piloted simulation.

The first method (termed mode 1) of modifying the baseline guidance trajectory was to alter pathway troughs by the greatest elevation difference between sensor-derived inertial database altitude and DMA-based altitude around a given trough (i.e. δ_{max}^n for trough n of Fig. 3). If there were no height values stored in the sensor-generated database in

Fig. 3. Path Manager Obstacle Avoidance Modes.

a considered radius, that trough position remained unchanged. This situation was common when approaching a hill that the trajectory (and thus the troughs) intended to pass over. Because the sensor could not look over the hill, it was unable to provide any obstacle information on the far side of the hill that could serve to reposition the (over the hill) troughs. This is the situation shown in Fig. 3, where troughs 5 - 7 are not moved from their baseline system trajectory locations.

The second path manager mode differed in how it managed troughs placed in areas where there was an absence of any sensor-generated data, e.g. those on the far side of a hill. Those troughs with at least one "filled" sensor grid in its diameter are repositioned, as in mode 1, by adding the maximum elevation difference (δ_{max}^n). Troughs without any sensor strikes (i.e. all grid values in the particular trough's diameter still initialized to -1) were altered by the average value of the local averages, i.e. $\bar{\delta}_{ave} = \sum_n \delta_{ave}^n$, for

the maximum difference altered troughs. Such special treatment of otherwise uncorrected trajectory sections was intended to reduce rapid and extreme jumps of the trajectory as sensor returns become available, as severe jumps of the trajectory presentation would be undesirable to a pilot. In the scenario of Fig. 3, this results in a somewhat higher trajectory in troughs 5 - 7 (those downstream of the hill) than that of mode 1.

The third approach considered for the path manager was an aircraft performance limited version of mode 2. The trajectory troughs are vertically repositioned as in mode 2, but also constrained in climb and dive angle and vertical load factor, at the limits selected by the pilot for the baseline guidance system trajectory. If a sequence of troughs exceeded those limits, that sequence and any additional troughs were moved vertically to conform while still clearing the obstacles. As an example, should the trajectory attempt to clear a tall tree set in flat terrain, the path manager

in mode 2 would lift only that trough nearest the tree and minimally lift the remaining trajectory troughs. This would create a trajectory with only one trough displaced by (essentially) the height of the tree, looking quite literally like a lone hurdle on a track. In mode 3 of the path manager, however, those trajectory troughs on each side of the affected trough would also be raised to present a smoothed, ramped up then down trajectory compatible with the aircraft performance limits (Fig. 3).

SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

The motion-based, piloted simulation of the forward-sensor enhanced guidance system was conducted in the NASA Vertical Motion Simulator (VMS), a six degree-of-freedom full-motion facility. The simulation experiment was conducted over a five week period during October and early November 1992. The cockpit environment is shown as Fig. 4. The pilot is shown with the IHADSS helmet-mounted display and a head-down color moving-map display (at the left center of the instrument panel). Conventional cyclic, collective, rudder pedals, and a limited number of aircraft instruments were provided similar to those of a UH-60 Blackhawk helicopter. The helicopter model employed was a 10 degree of freedom, nonlinear blade element model of a UH-60 Blackhawk [12]. Stability augmentation control systems and integrated GPS and inertial navigation systems were also modeled.

An Evans and Sutherland CT5A provided three-window computer generated imagery (CGI) for the pilot. The CGI database flown was generated from a Level I DMA DTED database of the Carlisle, PA area from 77° to 78° W longitude and from 40° to 41° N latitude. The imagery's representation of the terrain was generated by considering every other DMA DTED elevation "post", i.e. every 6 arc sec by 6 arc sec. This database was enhanced by the addition of randomly placed trees of 85 and 95 ft height. Occasional buildings were also added at some course waypoints. This (tree and building) obstacle enriched CGI database was then uniformly sampled off line at 33 ft (10 m) spacing for use by the forward sensor. This substituted for the real-world scene of Fig. 1. Recall that the baseline CALAHF guidance system employs only the DMA database values, and thus does not consider the obstacles in generating its trajectories. In this manner, the essential characteristics and interaction of the forward sensor, baseline guidance system, obstacles, and DMA database are represented.

Table 1 describes the matrix of test conditions studied. The first two evaluation configurations were of the baseline system. Configuration 1, the nominal condition during much of the development of the CALAHF guidance system, allowed the evaluation pilots to train and re-acquaint

Fig. 4. Flight Simulator Cockpit Arrangement.

themselves with the guidance system and pilot display. For this condition, the aircraft was initialized to 300 ft set clearance, 80 kts, and placed in 1 n. mi visibility. In order to have a basis for comparison of the forward sensor enhancement, configuration 2 was evaluated. This 90 kts, 50 ft set clearance altitude configuration placed the aircraft below the height of the trees and obstacles of the CGI. The pilot's task during both of these configurations was to fly the generated guidance trajectory as presented on the helmet mounted display. Any obstacles encountered were to be recognized and avoided at the pilot's discretion.

Configurations 3 through 5 considered the three modes of incorporating the forward sensor into the terrain referenced guidance system. Each was flown at 50 ft set clearance altitude at 90 kts with 1 n. mi visibility. The forward sensor was set to 25° x 50° FOV, 1° resolution, and 4922 ft range as described previously. Sensor parameters were altered for configurations 6 and 7. In order to determine performance degradation with less capable sensors, the maximum range of the forward sensor was clipped to 1969 ft (600 m) with the same 25° x 50° FOV for configuration 6, but left at 4922 ft range for the reduced 2° x 2° FOV of configuration 7. Shorter range capability or field of view typically translate to reduced cost and complexity in an obstacle sensor. The piloting task during the sensor enhanced configurations was that of tracking the (now) obstacle avoidance capable trajectory through the pilot symbology.

Table 1. Flight Simulation Test Conditions.

Config. #	Airspeed (kts)	Obstacle Avoidance	Clearance Altitude (ft)	Visibility (n. mi)	Sensor	Comments
1	80	Off	300	1	n/a	baseline system
2	90	Off	50	1	n/a	baseline system
3	90	Mode 1	50	1	nominal	
4	90	Mode 2	50	1	nominal	
5	90	Mode 3	50	1	nominal	
6	90	Mode 3	50	1	1969 ft range	
7	90	Mode 3	50	1	2° x 2° FOV	
8	90	Mode 3	50	5	nominal	+ target task

In the final test configuration, visibility was increased to 5 n. mi and a secondary pilot task was added. The path manager was placed in mode 3 with the forward sensor returned to nominal performance. Ground and air targets for pilot identification were placed along the test course. The targets were placed at an average range of 4000 ft and generally within a 10° azimuth from the current aircraft heading. Airborne targets were placed at the aircraft set clearance altitude above the terrain. The four target types were to be identified as friend (AH-1 helicopter, M-1 tank), or foe (Mi-24 helicopter, Zsu-23 rocket launcher) by pushing one of two buttons on the collective control. The targets were nominally placed every 2 min and remained on for 30 sec, during which time the pilot was to identify the friend or foe nature of the target. In this configuration, the piloting task was to track the obstacle sensitive guidance trajectory while maintaining situational awareness, as represented by the identification task. The workload associated with this additional task was designed to simulate the extra workload inherent in a real flight environment.

Guidance system conditions that remained constant throughout the flight simulation included maximum climb / dive angles (both 6°), maximum bank angle (20°), normal load factor ($0.75 < n_z < 1.25$), moderate 8 ft rms Dryden turbulence [13], and "TF/TA ratio" of 0.1. The TF/TA ratio sets the relative degree of lateral and vertical maneuvering of the guidance trajectory. A TF/TA ratio of 0.1 gives a "moderate" blend of vertical and lateral movement. All test configurations were evaluated over the same section of the modeled Carlisle, PA area. Data collection experimental runs were of 5 min duration for configurations 1 through 7, and of 20 min for configuration 8.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several pilots from NASA, the U.S. Army, and the airframe industry flew the forward sensor-enhanced system through the eight test configurations detailed in Table 1. Performance was assessed by monitoring pilot tracking of the guidance trajectory and by soliciting qualitative ratings from the pilots. A summary of these ratings for the various test configurations is provided as Table 2. The first two pilot columns are the ratings provided by the NASA research pilot co-authors of this work, while the remaining three are those of test pilots from the airframe industry. The ratings of Table 2 for a given configuration are the result of multiple runs. Due to limited simulation time and pilot availability, some of the conditions were not evaluated by all of the pilots.

The modified Cooper-Harper (C-H) scale assigns a value from 1 (best) to 10 (worst) based on the pilot's assessment of aircraft characteristics and workload in meeting two defined levels of performance [14]. In our study, "adequate" performance was defined as tracking the displayed guidance symbology to within the trajectory trough width and height, i.e. a one standard deviation lateral error within 100 ft and one standard deviation vertical error within 50 ft. "Desired" performance was established at half this level, i.e. lateral error within 50 ft and vertical 25 ft. A pilot meeting the adequate level of performance would assign a C-H value between 5 and 7, depending on his assessment of aircraft characteristics and workload demands required in achieving that performance. Adequate performance achieved through "considerable pilot compensation" earns a 5, while "extensive pilot compensation" warrants a 6. Similarly, desired performance obtained with "moderate pilot compensation" yields a C-H rating of 4, and that where pilot compensation is "not a factor" is labeled a 1. Inherent during all runs was the requirement that the pilot not collide with either the ground or obstacles, which would result in a rating of 10.

Table 2. Pilot Cooper-Harper Ratings of Test Conditions.

Config. #	Description*	Pilot A	Pilot B	Pilot C	Pilot D	Pilot E
1	baseline 300 ft	2.5	4	4	4	3
2	baseline 50 ft	6	4	5	4	4
3	O.A. Mode 1	-	-	-	-	-
4	O.A. Mode 2	5.5	-	-	-	-
5	O.A. Mode 3	4	4	4	4	3
6	1969 ft range sensor	5	4	5	4	3
7	2° x 2° FOV sensor	4.5	4	-	-	-
8	target task	4.5	4	4	4	3

* see Table 1 for complete configuration descriptions.

The baseline CALAHF guidance system at 80 kts, 300 ft set clearance altitude (config. 1) earned a C-H rating from 2.5 to 4 (Table 2). The desired level of trajectory tracking was obtained by all of the test pilots with varying levels of pilot compensation required. At this flight altitude, nearly all of the CGI obstacles (except occasional buildings at waypoints) were below the generated trajectory and did not need to be avoided. This range of C-H ratings for this configuration duplicated earlier results obtained during previous flight simulations of the CALAHF system [6], and thus served to demonstrate the repeatability of the test environment and lend credibility to the other experimental configurations.

The lower altitude (50 ft) baseline system run (config. 2), which now required the pilot to observe and avoid obstacles in addition to tracking the guidance trajectory symbology, generally resulted in a higher C-H by at least 1 point, and by several points in one case. In this configuration the pilot task was to track the guidance trajectory symbology in addition to identifying and avoiding obstacles. The integration of the forward sensor (in later configurations) into the baseline CALAHF guidance system was intended to alleviate some of this additional workload of the system by performing the obstacle detection and avoidance duty.

The approach of modes 1 and 2 where only one trough of the guidance trajectory is altered was found very disruptive and unsatisfying to the pilots. The isolated and abrupt "spike" of one trough, among an otherwise smooth trajectory presentation, caused the pilot to doubt the accuracy of the trajectory and resulted in poor pilot acceptability. A lateral pass around the obstacle or a gentle climb and descent over the obstacle was suggested. The evaluation pilots found very little difference between path manager modes 1 and 2; the "spiking" of the trajectory over obstacles over-

shadowed the subtle attempt toward smoothing over the hill trajectories.

In considering the three path manager modes of modifying the guidance trajectory to avoid sensor identified obstacles, mode 3 (config. 5) was without question the preferred approach. It was found to effectively alter the terrain-referenced guidance trajectories over the obstacles identified by the forward sensor. The smooth ramping of trajectory troughs upstream and downstream of the lone obstacle affected trough by vertical acceleration and climb / dive angle limiting was found essential, and garnered confidence as a reliable and logical obstacle sensitive guidance trajectory system. Many of the pilots felt that this mode 3 configuration required no additional workload than the higher altitude (no obstacle) baseline system configuration (Table 2).

A typical ground track of the mode 3 forward sensor enhanced CALAHF guidance system (config. 5 of Table 1) is shown as Fig. 5. The solid line traces the northeast to southwest route flown, and the dots represent the trees placed in the CGI database. Potentially hazardous trees are lettered. Note that this overhead view does not depict the vertical obstacle avoidance maneuvers resulting from the forward sensor integration.

The companion vertical profile of the ground track is given as Fig. 6. The lower solid line tracks the terrain elevation, while the lettered "barber poles" depict three tree obstacles. The actual aircraft MSL altitude (solid line) and that commanded by the guidance system (dashed line) are also presented. The climb / dive angle and vertical acceleration constraints applied to the vertical repositioning of the trajectory is clearly evident as the aircraft negotiates trees A, D, and E. It is apparent that the actual path flown by the aircraft does not exactly match that computed and presented to the pilot. Although the trajectory commanded is constrained to be within the aircraft's performance capabilities, the pilot can never track the symbology perfectly, and at times will override the recommended pathway. Circumvention of the commanded trajectory occurs most often when an obstacle is encountered. At times the pilot flies closer or more aggressively near a tree to reduce high altitude exposure or to conserve fuel. Such pilot discretion in flying the recommended trajectory displayed on the HMD is typical and encouraged, as it allows the pilot to perform the maneuvers that he feels are appropriate as he flies the recommended trajectory and to the accuracy that he feels is necessary.

Two suggestions for improving the use of the forward sensor obstacle detection integration were prevalent. The pilots would have preferred some type of identification, perhaps outlining, of obstacles that were not a direct threat to the presented guidance trajectory. Although registered

Fig. 5. Flight Simulation Ground Track.

by the forward sensor and stored in its database, nearby obstacles were not identified to the pilot, although such obstacles could be hazardous. This is apparent when trees B and C of Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 are considered. These trees, although very close to the aircraft and clearly a hazard, produced no change to the stored terrain-based trajectory. A second suggestion was to allow lateral maneuvers when repositioning the trajectory in the event of obstacles. The approach in this study was to secure the terrain database generated trajectory from terrain and obstacle collision by vertically repositioning the appropriate trajectory troughs. In the military application, it is preferable to stay low and close to the terrain, in order to reduce the exposure time to ground-based

threats. Obstacle avoidance with lateral maneuvering is considered as part of related NASA helicopter flight automation research [15].

The reduced sensor range system (config. 6) was found to slightly degrade the performance and increase the workload of some of the pilots (Table 2). This was caused by occasional "jumping" during repositioning of the trajectory troughs upon processing of new obstacle data by the forward sensor. This was particularly evident when climbing over hills or negotiating a heading change at a waypoint, where a longer range sensor is most beneficial. In such situations, a longer sensor range is recommended.

Configuration 7, the narrow ($2^\circ \times 2^\circ$) FOV scenario, was evaluated extensively by only two of the evaluation pilots. Problems induced by this sensor were not as apparent as that of the reduced range case, suggesting that sensor range is more crucial for low-altitude obstacle avoidance than field-of-view. This may, however, be more reflective of the rather sparse number of obstacles involved in the test, and the rather simplistic line-of-sight sensor model, which required only one strike from one beam for obstacle detection.

The secondary workload scenario (config. 8) produced essentially no degradation in workload or tracking performance than that without the additional workload (config. 5). The pilots were able to perform the detection and identification of targets while flying the mode 3 obstacle sensitive guidance trajectory with relative ease. This supported the suitability of the forward sensor-enhanced guidance system in a flight-realistic workload environment.

Fig. 6. Flight Simulation Vertical Profile.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

1) A simulated forward sensor has been integrated into a low-altitude terrain-following / terrain-avoidance (TF/TA) guidance system to allow reduced operating altitudes. The enhanced system detected and processed obstacles automatically and was evaluated in a piloted, motion-based flight simulation. The results demonstrate that pilot performance and workload of this augmented system was similar to the baseline system.

2) The sensor-enhanced system successfully applied vertical adjustments to the nominal TF/TA guidance trajectory to avoid obstacles under a variety of test conditions. Vertical trajectory modifications subject to climb / dive angle and normal load factor performance constraints were found to be preferred. Missions of 50 ft altitude at 90 kts airspeed under reduced visibility and moderate turbulence were considered, in addition to flights involving a secondary workload task.

3) Although bolstered by the added obstacle avoidance capability of the baseline TF/TA guidance system studied, the evaluation pilots felt that even better use could be made of the detected obstacle information. It was suggested that the obstacles should be identified, perhaps outlined, for pilot monitoring of the automatic obstacle avoidance. The ability to perform lateral as well as vertical obstacle avoidance maneuvers was also recommended.

Future work will include flight evaluation of the forward sensor-enhanced guidance system aboard the Army NUH-60A STAR helicopter and further development of the sensor integration approach. A more sophisticated means of creating a quantized obstacle/terrain grid database, e.g. combining multiple measurements in the same inertial grid space, accounting for placement within a given grid square, and considering the influence of neighboring grid height values, will also be studied.

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